

SUPPLEMENT A

SUPPLEMENT A.1

Each experiment was designed so that the work time per participant would be limited to approximately one hour taking into consideration the physical and mental burden on the participants.

SUPPLEMENT A.1-1 COLLECTION

In this *Collection* step, the details of the definitions of the number of participants are as follows:

$(20 \text{ participants}) \times (20 \text{ tasks (pair of recipes)}) / (67 \text{ pairs of recipes}) = 5.97$, therefore, approximately five participants, on average, checked each pair of recipes.

SUPPLEMENT A.1-2 AGGREGATION

In this *Aggregation* step, the details of the definitions of the number of participants are as follows:

The number of combinations of 426 content candidates are ${}_{426}C_2 = 90,525$.

$370 \text{ (participants)} \times 25 \text{ (tasks)} \times 100 \text{ (pairs of content candidates)} / 90,525 = 10.22$, therefore, approximately 10 participants, on average, checked each pair of content candidate.

It is because future research might involve supporting people's efforts to describe the extracted content categories, the threshold value of the similarity (i.e., "Pairs of content candidates that four or more study participants judged to be similar were considered similar") was set so that the number of content categories (see Section 5.2.2) would be between five and nine [ref1], which is the number of elements that humans can retain using short-term memory.

[ref1] Miller, George A. 1956. The magical number seven, plus or minus two: Some limits on our capacity for processing information. *Psychol. Rev.* 63, 2, 81–97.

SUPPLEMENT A.1-3 CONCEPTUALIZATION

In this *Conceptualization* step, among six content categories which were identified, only "reasons for tools used" was renamed to "reasons for the cooking process," based on this study's intent.

SUPPLEMENT A.2

As the first qualitative evaluation, we asked 400 participants, “Do you think the recipes mentioning each category are useful?” using a 10-point Likert scale (10: Useful – 1: Useless). The mean (SD) scores were 8.16 (1.80) for reasons, 8.48 (1.51) for suitable ingredients, 9.02 (1.22) for notes, 8.39 (1.65) for substitutions, 8.33 (1.68) for variations, and 6.98 (2.06) for servings. For the second qualitative evaluation, we issued a free-form questionnaire to 200 participants, asking, “What kind of content is included in useful cooking recipes?” One annotator confirmed whether each content category was mentioned (multiple categories allowed). The percentages were 17% for reasons, 43% for suitable ingredients, 60% for notes, 26% for substitutions, 35% for variations, and 5% for servings. In summary, all content categories were mentioned as useful.

SUPPLEMENT B

Table S-1. The number of each type of experimental recipes created for each content category

Content category	Deleted recipe	Arrangement				
		A01	A02	A03	A04	A05
reasons	13	13	9	5	13	13
suitable ingredients	40	40	40	40	40	40
notes	40	39	40	32	40	40
substitutions	21	21	21	21	21	21
variations	44	44	44	17	44	44
servings	30	30	30	1	30	30

When the deleted recipes were created, a minimal expression adjustment was made only when the recipe became grammatically incorrect when the sentences indicating the corresponding content category were deleted. When the rearranged recipes were created, if a rearranged recipe was the same as the original, it was not created. We did not create deleted or rearranged recipes for content categories that were not included in the relevant original recipe.

As a result, the number of each type of experimental recipes created for each content category were shown in the Table S-1. To avoid bias in the number of times each arrangement of content categories was used in the experiments in Section 6.2 and 6.3, we randomly selected 13 experimental documents from all the arrangements of content categories in Table S-1 and used them in the experiments in Section 6.2 and 6.3. For the arrangement of content categories reasons_A02, reasons_A03, and servings_A03, for which there were fewer than 13 experimental recipes, all the corresponding experimental recipes were used. Therefore, a total of 444 pairs of the deleted recipe and the original recipe or five types of rearranged recipes were discussed in this analysis.

SUPPLEMENT C

SUPPLEMENT C.1 The number of participants

300 (participants) × 25 (tasks for Step 1 or 2)/444 tasks = 16.89, therefore, approximately over 15 participants, on average, checked each pair of content candidate.

SUPPLEMENT C.2 Details of data obtained and used

Raw data (7,500 answers)

participant_ID	task no	usefulness score	unknown words	understandability	skill level	Information needs (reasons)	Information needs (suitable ingredients)	...
Id_001	1	1	1	8	8	8	7	
Id_001	2	2	0	8	7	8	7	
⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	
Id_001	25	0	1	10	6	8	7	
Id_002	1	-2	0	9	8	9	9	
Id_002	2	1	0	8	6	9	9	
⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	

Each participant repeated 25 tasks, and 300 participants answered.

There were some defects.

Data used for Analysis in Section 6.3 (5,574 answers)

participant_ID	task no	usefulness score	unknown words	understandability	skill level	Information needs (reasons)	Information needs (suitable ingredients)	...
Id_001	1	1	1	8	8	8	7	
⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	
Id_001	25	0	1	10	6	8	7	
Id_002	2	1	0	8	6	9	9	
⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	

Figure S-1. The details of raw data obtained in Section 6.2. and the data used in Section 6.3.

SUPPLEMENT D

SUPPLEMENT D.1 Results for selecting models

Table 3. The interclass correlation coefficient (ICC) and the design effect (DE) for each data.

	ICC	DE		ICC	DE
the presence or absence of unknown words (1: exist – 0: not exist)	0.03	17.3	the information needs for <i>reasons</i>	0.01	2.17
the number of unknown words	0.08	10.1	the information needs for <i>suitable ingredients</i>	0.00	1.00
the understandings	0.00	1.00	the information needs for <i>notes</i>	0.00	1.50
the skill levels	0.00	1.10	the information needs for <i>substitutions</i>	0.00	1.00
			the information needs for <i>variations</i>	0.08	10.0
			the information needs for <i>servings</i>	0.01	2.20

SUPPLEMENT D.2 Results for selecting models

The WAIC scores of each model are shown in Table S-2. All \hat{R} were under 1.05.

Table S-2. WAIC values for each model

	Reasons	Suitable ingredients	Notes	Substitutions	Variations	Servings
Model original	14744.9	14742.1	14674.0	14742.0	14748.5	14752.0
Model A01	14746.7	14745.4	14681.3	14742.1	14749.0	14753.0
Model A02	14744.2	14741.3	14687.2	14741.3	14750.6	14751.3
Model A03	14746.5	14733.3	14680.7	14741.7	14747.1	14751.6
Model A04	14745.5	14741.7	14681.3	14746.8	14749.7	14748.6
Model A05	14746.6	14742.1	14682.3	14741.2	14750.1	14751.3

SUPPLEMENT D.3 Results of parameter fittings

The details of the results for the model with the smallest WAIC for each content category were shown in Table S-3 – Table S-8.

Table S-3. The estimation results of Model A02 for reasons

Population-Level Effects:					
	Estimate	Est.Error	l-95% CI	U-95% CI	Rhat
Intercept	0.37	0.60	-1.01	1.63	1.00
original (β_1)	0.00	0.01	-0.01	0.02	1.00
A01 (β_2)	-0.01	0.01	-0.03	0.00	1.00
A02 (β_3)	-0.03	0.78	-1.83	1.67	1.00
A03 (β_4)	0.01	0.01	-0.01	0.04	1.00
A04 (β_5)	-0.01	0.01	-0.03	0.00	1.00
A05 (β_6)	-0.01	0.01	-0.02	0.01	1.00
Family Specific Parameters:					

sigma	0.91	0.01	0.89	0.92	1.00
Group-Level Effects					
the presence of unknown words in reasons					
sd (η_3)	0.63	0.99	0.01	3.43	1.01
sd (γ_3)	0.81	1.04	0.01	3.78	1.00
Corr (η_3, γ_3)	0.02	0.63	-0.96	0.98	1.00

Table S-4. The estimation results of Model A02 for suitable ingredients

Population-Level Effects:					
	Estimate	Est.Error	l-95% CI	U-95% CI	Rhat
Intercept	0.32	0.61	-1.15	1.53	1.00
original (β_1)	-0.02	0.01	-0.03	-0.00	1.00
A01 (β_2)	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.03	1.00
A02 (β_3)	-0.01	0.01	-0.02	0.01	1.00
A03 (β_4)	0.05	1.12	-2.36	2.55	1.00
A04 (β_5)	-0.00	0.01	-0.02	0.01	1.00
A05 (β_6)	-0.00	0.01	-0.02	0.01	1.00
Family Specific Parameters:					
sigma	0.91	0.01	0.89	0.92	1.00
Group-Level Effects					
the presence of unknown words in suitable ingredients					
sd (η_3)	0.71	1.02	0.01	3.45	1.00
sd (γ_3)	1.12	1.28	0.08	4.73	1.00
Corr (η_3, γ_3)	-0.08	0.60	-0.98	0.95	1.00

Table S-5. The estimation results of Model original for notes

Population-Level Effects:					
	Estimate	Est.Error	l-95% CI	U-95% CI	Rhat
Intercept	0.31	0.63	-1.27	1.46	1.00
original (β_1)	-0.05	0.81	-1.96	1.71	1.00
A01 (β_2)	0.03	0.01	0.01	0.04	1.00
A02 (β_3)	-0.04	0.01	-0.05	-0.02	1.00
A03 (β_4)	0.03	0.01	0.01	0.04	1.00
A04 (β_5)	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.03	1.00
A05 (β_6)	0.01	0.01	-0.01	0.02	1.00
Family Specific Parameters:					
sigma	0.90	0.01	0.88	0.92	1.00
Group-Level Effects					
the presence of unknown words in notes					
sd (η_1)	0.66	1.00	0.01	3.42	1.00
sd (γ_1)	0.83	1.01	0.04	3.81	1.00

Corr (η_1, γ_1)	0.01	0.63	-0.98	0.98	1.00
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Table S-6. The estimation results of Model A05 for substitutions

Population-Level Effects:					
	Estimate	Est.Error	l-95% CI	U-95% CI	Rhat
Intercept	0.32	0.71	-1.24	1.79	1.00
original (β_1)	-0.01	0.01	-0.02	0.00	1.00
A01 (β_2)	-0.01	0.01	-0.02	0.01	1.00
A02 (β_3)	-0.01	0.01	-0.03	0.00	1.00
A03 (β_4)	-0.00	0.01	-0.02	0.01	1.00
A04 (β_5)	-0.00	0.01	-0.02	0.01	1.00
A05 (β_6)	-0.05	0.72	-2.08	1.50	1.00
Family Specific Parameters:					
sigma	0.91	0.01	0.89	0.92	1.00
Group-Level Effects					
the presence of unknown words in substitutions					
sd (η_6)	0.70	1.07	0.01	3.67	1.01
sd (γ_6)	0.75	1.14	0.01	4.02	1.00
Corr (η_6, γ_6)	-0.04	0.63	-0.98	0.97	1.00

Table S-7. The estimation results of Model original for variations

Population-Level Effects:					
	Estimate	Est.Error	l-95% CI	U-95% CI	Rhat
Intercept	0.37	0.60	-1.03	1.65	1.00
original (β_1)	-0.03	0.71	-1.57	1.54	1.00
A01 (β_2)	0.00	0.01	-0.01	0.02	1.00
A02 (β_3)	-0.01	0.01	-0.03	0.00	1.00
A03 (β_4)	-0.00	0.01	-0.02	0.01	1.00
A04 (β_5)	0.00	0.01	-0.01	0.02	1.00
A05 (β_6)	-0.00	0.01	-0.01	0.01	1.00
Family Specific Parameters:					
sigma	0.91	0.01	0.89	0.92	1.00
Group-Level Effects					
the presence of unknown words in variations					
sd (η_1)	0.62	0.94	0.01	3.31	1.00
sd (γ_1)	0.64	0.90	0.01	3.23	1.00
Corr (η_1, γ_1)	0.00	0.63	-0.98	0.98	1.00

Table S-8_1. The estimation results of Model A02 for servings

Population-Level Effects:					
	Estimate	Est.Error	l-95% CI	U-95% CI	Rhat
Intercept	0.38	0.53	-0.82	1.58	1.00
original (β_1)	-0.00	0.01	-0.01	0.01	1.00
A01 (β_2)	0.00	0.01	-0.01	0.02	1.00
A02 (β_3)	-0.01	0.66	-1.64	1.33	1.00
A03 (β_4)	0.00	0.03	-0.05	0.07	1.00
A04 (β_5)	0.01	0.01	-0.00	0.02	1.00
A05 (β_6)	0.00	0.01	-0.01	0.02	1.00
Family Specific Parameters:					
sigma	0.91	0.01	0.89	0.92	1.00
Group-Level Effects					
the presence of unknown words in servings					
sd (η_3)	0.60	0.92	0.01	3.22	1.00
sd (γ_3)	0.64	0.97	0.01	3.42	1.00
Corr (η_3, γ_3)	-0.04	0.62	-0.98	0.97	1.00

Table S-8_2. The estimation results of Model A05 for servings

Population-Level Effects:					
	Estimate	Est.Error	l-95% CI	U-95% CI	Rhat
Intercept	0.41	0.61	-0.81	1.72	1.00
original (β_1)	-0.00	0.01	-0.01	0.01	1.00
A01 (β_2)	0.00	0.01	-0.01	0.02	1.00
A02 (β_3)	0.00	0.01	-0.01	0.02	1.00
A03 (β_4)	0.01	0.03	-0.04	0.07	1.00
A04 (β_5)	0.01	0.01	-0.00	0.03	1.00
A05 (β_6)	0.01	0.63	-1.29	1.57	1.00
Family Specific Parameters:					
sigma	0.91	0.01	0.89	0.92	1.00
Group-Level Effects					
the presence of unknown words in servings					
sd (η_6)	0.61	0.88	0.01	3.18	1.00
sd (γ_6)	0.66	0.92	0.01	3.35	1.01
Corr (η_6, γ_6)	0.02	0.63	-0.97	0.98	1.00